

Vascular smooth muscle cells in hypoxic pulmonary hypertension

In memory of more than twenty years of cooperation with Prof. Jan Herget

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Summary

Pulmonary hypertension is a complex and heterogeneous condition that can be divided into 5 subtypes according to the ESC/ERS guidelines. These subtypes comprise Group 1 – pulmonary arterial hypertension, Group 2 – pulmonary hypertension associated with left heart disease, Group 3 – pulmonary hypertension associated with lung diseases and/or hypoxia, Group 4 – pulmonary hypertension associated with pulmonary artery obstructions, and Group 5 – pulmonary hypertension with unclear and/or multifactorial mechanisms. This review article is concentrated on hypoxic pulmonary hypertension (HPH), belonging to Group 3. It is based mainly on our own experimental work, i.e. on our collaboration with the group of Professor Herget and his followers. The work is presented in the context of worldwide HPH research, and includes some of our previously unpublished results. In particular, we focused on the role of vascular smooth muscle cells (VSMCs) in pulmonary artery remodeling in HPH. We investigated the effect of extracellular matrix damaged by oxidation and degradation, namely by ultraviolet light, direct action of metalloproteinases, macrophages and mast cells (normoxic and hypoxia-activated), on VSMC adhesion and growth *in vitro*. We also isolated VSMCs from the pulmonary arteries of normoxic and hypoxic rats, and compared their growth and the expression of differentiation markers under normoxic and hypoxic conditions *in vitro*. We conclude that all factors studied, such as oxidation and degradation of extracellular matrix, in the presence or absence of pro-inflammatory cells, have a positive effect on the activation of VSMC proliferation. However, hypoxia has a dual effect: on the one hand, it can activate VSMC proliferation and hyperplasia, but on the other hand, it can also induce VSMC hypertrophy and increased expression of contractile markers in these cells. The influence of hypoxia-inducible factors, microRNAs and galectin-3 in the initiation and development of HPH, and the role of cell types other than VSMCs (endothelial cells, adventitial fibroblasts) in this disease are also discussed. Attention is also paid to the treatment options for HPH.

Keywords: oxidation, degradation, extracellular matrix, collagen, proteolytic enzymes, metalloproteinases, macrophages, mast cells, smooth muscle cells, endothelial cells, fibroblasts, mesenchymal stem cells, hypoxia-inducible factor, microRNA, galectins, vasoconstriction, remodeling, therapy of hypoxic pulmonary hypertension

1. Introduction

Pulmonary hypertension is defined according to the 2022 ESC/ERS Guidelines for the diagnosis and treatment of pulmonary hypertension as a mean pulmonary artery pressure (mPAP) greater than 20 mmHg at rest [1]. Pulmonary hypertension is a complex, heterogeneous disease with various subtypes, i.e. with different etiology, manifestations, course and prognosis, which can be classified from different perspectives, such as etiological, pathological and diagnostic points of view (for a review, see [2-5]).

From the etiological point of view, there is a distinction between primary and secondary pulmonary hypertension. Primary pulmonary hypertension is characterized by the involvement of small arteries, the cause of which is unclear and is thought to be primary damage to the endothelium of the pulmonary vasculature. The disease develops mainly in younger women and has a poor prognosis (patients usually die of right-sided heart failure within 3 years) (for a review, see [5,6]).

Secondary pulmonary hypertension arises from another underlying disease. In terms of hemodynamics and pathophysiology, pulmonary hypertension can be distinguished as pre-capillary, post-capillary and hyperkinetic. Precapillary hypertension typically occurs in pulmonary diseases (chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, pulmonary fibrosis, sarcoidosis, pneumoconiosis), chronic pulmonary embolism, after lung resection, in pulmonary hypoventilation, and also in the case of vasculitis in systemic connective tissue diseases. In postcapillary pulmonary hypertension, the cause lies in left-sided heart disease (left-sided heart failure, mitral stenosis, hypertrophic cardiomyopathy) or constrictive pericarditis. Hyperkinetic pulmonary hypertension is often caused by left-right heart shunts such as persistent ductus arteriosus, atrial or ventricular septal defects, or conditions with high cardiac output (for example, hyperthyroidism) (for a review, see [2,3,6]).

From the pathological point of view, a recent classification defines categories of pulmonary hypertension according to the values of mean arterial pulmonary pressure (mPAP), pulmonary arterial wedge pressure (PAWP), and pulmonary vascular resistance (PVR; **Table 1**).

Table 1. Categories of pulmonary hypertension (PH; adapted from [7])

Definition	Haemodynamic characteristics		
	mPAP	PAWP	PVR
Pulmonary Hypertension (PH)	>20 mmHg		
Pre-capillary PH	>20 mmHg	≤15 mmHg	> 2 WU
Isolated post-capillary PH	>20 mmHg	>15 mmHg	≤ 2 WU
Combined post-and pre-capillary PH	>20 mmHg	>15 mmHg	> 2 WU
Unclassified PH	>20 mmHg	≤15 mmHg	≤2 WU
Exercise PH	mPAP/CO slope between rest and exercise > 3 mmHg/L/min		

From the diagnostic point of view, i.e. in terms of the causes, prognosis and therapy of the disease, and according to the 2022 ESC/ERS Guidelines for the diagnosis and treatment of pulmonary hypertension, we distinguish the following five groups of pulmonary hypertension [1]:

Group 1: Pulmonary arterial hypertension (PAH). This is pre-capillary hypertension [4], the cause of which lies primarily in the pulmonary vasculature. An adverse remodeling of the pulmonary artery walls occurs, especially hypertrophy of the smooth muscle of the *tunica media*, as well as abnormal

behavior of other cell types such as endothelial cells, fibroblasts and pro-inflammatory cells. The incidence of this disease is fortunately relatively low. Idiopathic pulmonary arterial hypertension is the most common subtype, followed by connective tissue disease and porto-pulmonary hypertension (for a review, see [1,2,8,9]).

Group 2: Pulmonary hypertension associated with left heart disease, which is the most common type of pulmonary hypertension. In left-sided heart failure or mitral valve stenosis, increased blood pressure propagates from the left atrium into the pulmonary circulation. Initially, the pressure in the left atrium is increased and post-capillary hypertension develops [4], but later the pressure in the pulmonary artery may increase, resulting in combined pre- and post-capillary pulmonary hypertension (for a review, see [2,3]).

Group 3: Pulmonary hypertension associated with lung disease and/or hypoxemia. This is the second most common type of pulmonary hypertension, where the primary disease is in the lungs rather than in the pulmonary arterial system, or it is chronic mountain sickness. It is pre-capillary hypertension [4], which occurs at high altitudes [10] or in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), obstructive sleep apnea syndrome, and interstitial pulmonary fibrosis (for a review, see [2,3,11-13]). Chronic exposure to cigarette smoke can also lead to this type of pulmonary hypertension [14,15]. In comparison with PAH (group 1), which is progressive and irreversible, the pulmonary vascular remodeling during hypoxic pulmonary hypertension is milder and is largely thought to be reversible, although some patients can also develop severe pulmonary hypertension with irreversible vascular remodeling similar to that in the group 1 disease [16].

Group 4: Pulmonary hypertension associated with chronic pulmonary artery obstruction (or chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension, CTEPH). This is pre-capillary hypertension [4], which occurs after pulmonary embolism. Despite adequate therapy, the thrombi are not sufficiently recanalised, and their reorganization, fibrotization, permanent attachment to the arterial wall and possible subsequent growth occur (for a review, see [2,3,17]).

Group 5: Pulmonary hypertension with unclear and/or multifactorial mechanisms: it is either pre-capillary or combined pre- and post-capillary hypertension [4]. It includes all unclassifiable causes of pulmonary hypertension, such as hematological disorders (e.g. hemolytic anemia, myeloproliferative disorders), metabolic disorders (glycogen storage disease, Gaucher's disease), systemic disorders (sarcoidosis, histiocytosis X) and cancer, or hypertension with a multifactorial or unclear cause (for a review, see [2,4,17]).

In our studies performed in collaboration with Professor Jan Herget's group, we focused on **hypoxic pulmonary hypertension** (HPH), which belongs to group 3 of the above-mentioned classification. Studies by Professor Jan Herget's group revealed that HPH can be induced by low oxygen partial pressure in the surrounding atmosphere, e.g. in an experimental hypoxic chamber simulating high altitudes [18,19], during airway obstruction [20], or in lung diseases, such as microbial and sterile inflammation [21], asthma or emphysema [22,23] or silicosis [24]. This “classic” spectrum of causes of HPH has recently been extended by another important cause, namely the novel coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19), which leads to asymptomatic chronic arterial hypoxemia and long-term cardiovascular complications. It is, therefore, likely that the prevalence of HPH will increase in the future, and research into this disease will rapidly gain great importance (for a review, see [13]).

There are two mechanisms involved in the onset and development of HPH: **hypoxic pulmonary vasoconstriction** and **hypoxic pulmonary vascular remodeling**, which may eventually lead to right heart failure or death (for a review, see [11]). Important actors in both these stages are vascular smooth

muscle cells (VSMCs). This review summarizes the role and behavior of VSMCs in both of these stages, particularly in the second stage, namely vascular wall remodeling.

2. VSMCs in hypoxic pulmonary vasoconstriction

The immediate response of pulmonary vessels to hypoxia, i.e., a decrease in alveolar oxygen pressure, is vasoconstriction [10,25]. This differs from systemic circulation, where the main response to hypoxia is vasodilation, caused by the stabilization of hypoxia-inducible factor-1 α (HIF-1 α), i.e. its avoidance of propyl hydroxylation [26], and concomitant upregulation of endothelial nitric oxide (NO) synthase. The reason is that the hypoxia in the lung primarily results from hypoventilation of circumscribed areas of the lung, e.g. by bronchial tree obstruction or inflammatory infiltration. Therefore, hypoxic pulmonary vasoconstriction is a mechanism preventing the distribution of blood to hypoventilated areas of the lungs, thereby maintaining maximal oxygenation of the blood [10,27].

Pulmonary vasoconstriction is a functional change in the pulmonary vasculature, mediated by VSMCs, and is completely reversible. Its mechanism is depolarization of the VSMC membrane and entry of calcium ions into the cells (for a review, see [11]). Another mechanism of hypoxic pulmonary vasoconstriction is the inhibition of NO synthase. This inhibition may be caused, at least partly, by the elevation of asymmetric dimethylarginine, an endogenous inhibitor of NO synthesis [27].

Pulmonary vasoconstriction can be reversed by repolarization of the cell membrane by activating calcium-gated potassium channels. Activators of these channels include, for example, dehydroepiandrosterone sulfate. This substance, given orally in drinking water, significantly reduced pulmonary blood pressure and peripheral pulmonary artery remodeling in rats [28]. Other substances inducing vascular relaxation include α -methyl dopa [18,29], NO [25] and drugs restoring or stimulating the effect of NO, such as statins (simvastatin [30]) or phosphodiesterase 5 inhibitors, e.g. sildenafil [31]. A vasorelaxant effect is also produced by hypercapnia, which accompanies hypoxia in the lung [32,33]. Adjustment of arterial tone to physiological values was also originally expected from an angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitor, namely Ramipril. However, it was found to alleviate rather the morphological remodeling of peripheral pulmonary arteries due to hypoxia [34].

3. VSMCs in structural remodeling of pulmonary vasculature

With prolonged duration or recurrence of hypoxia, morphological remodeling of pulmonary vessels, particularly peripheral, pre-alveolar vessels, follows [35]. The mechanism of this remodeling of the vascular wall during hypoxia involves, although it may seem somewhat paradoxical, the production of **reactive oxygen species** (ROS [36,37]), and also the production of **proteolytic enzymes** [38-40]. The effect of both of these factors ultimately simulates the proliferation of VSMCs, their hyperplasia, increased matrix deposition by these cells, and thickening of the vascular wall in pulmonary hypertension (for a review, see [10,11,41]).

3.1. Effects of ROS and macrophages

During hypoxia, ROS are produced by cells of the pulmonary vasculature, namely endothelial cells, VSMCs, adventitial fibroblasts [16,42,43], and also cells of the immune system, such as alveolar macrophages [36] and mast cells, infiltrating large and small pulmonary arteries and occurring subpleurally and perivascularly [38].

ROS have a dual effect on cells, including VSMCs. In higher concentrations, they can cause damage to the cell membrane, mitochondria, DNA or alteration of the function of various enzymes in the sense of their inhibition (protein kinase C) or activation (proteases and endonucleases). These

effects can then lead to cell growth arrest and cell death. However, dying cells and their surviving neighbors can produce growth factors and other biomolecules that ultimately stimulate the proliferation of the cell population originally damaged by oxidative stress. Moreover, at lower concentrations, ROS can directly stimulate cell proliferation. The mechanism of this effect is similar to that of growth factors. ROS can activate the receptor and non-receptor tyrosine kinases, mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK), transcription factor NF- κ B, the expression of proto-oncogenes c-fos, and c-jun, the apoptosis-regulating Bcl-2 gene, and also autocrine production of growth factors, which plays an important role in activating the growth of the VSMC population. Already in 1996, Burdon formulated the hypothesis that normal production of ROS is necessary for normal transduction of signals regulating cell growth [44]; for a review, see [15,45,46]. Mitochondria and nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADPH) oxidase are considered to be the major ROS producers in the cardiovascular system. In accordance with this, studies on VSMCs under normobaric hypoxia in both humans and animals have shown that the Nox4 isoform of the NADPH oxidase complex was overexpressed, which contributed to VSMC proliferation leading to pulmonary hypertension [10].

In addition, ROS can also stimulate VSMC proliferation indirectly by modifying their extracellular matrix (ECM). To explore this possibility, we developed a simple model of oxidative damage to the ECM *in vitro*, namely collagen irradiated with **ultraviolet (UV) light**. We used either type I collagen, which is the major ECM protein of the healthy vessel wall, or type III collagen, another important type of collagen in the blood vessel wall, whose content increases in a pathologically altered vascular wall, such as in hypertension. Although our research was primarily related to pulmonary hypertension, we initially used rat aortic smooth muscle cells as a cellular model because of their relatively easy isolation compared to pulmonary vascular cells [47,48].

We have found that UV light not only oxidized collagen but also degraded it into low molecular weight fragments. The adhesion of VSMCs to this collagen was weakened, which was reflected not only by their smaller spreading area but also by their higher susceptibility to detachment from the substrate by trypsin. Even molecular markers of cell adhesion differed between cells on irradiated collagen and on non-irradiated collagen. Cells on irradiated collagen had less developed focal adhesion plaques and contained lower concentrations of β_1 -integrins, which include receptors for collagen, and also lower concentrations of focal adhesion proteins talin and vinculin, contractile protein α -actin (i.e., a marker of VSMC differentiation) and cytoskeletal protein vimentin. At the same time, VSMCs proliferated faster on irradiated collagen, at least at lower population densities - at higher densities these differences disappeared. The faster proliferation of VSMCs was explained by the fact that the cells escaped the growth control provided by cell-matrix contact. In addition, VSMCs contained increased concentrations of immunoglobulin adhesion molecules such as intercellular cell adhesion molecule-1 (ICAM-1) and vascular cell adhesion molecule-1 (VCAM-1), which bind the cells of the immune system [47,48]. A similar pro-inflammatory phenotype of VSMCs, expressing ICAM-1 and producing various cytokines and chemokines, has also been described in the pulmonary arteries of human patients suffering from HPH as well as in animal models of this disease (for a review, see [49]).

Our research therefore also focused on **immune cells** and their influence on the ECM and on the adhesion and proliferation of VSMCs. As the first of these immune cells, we focused on **macrophages**, as these cells are known to play an important role in the origin and development of vascular diseases, and are an **important source of ROS**. For example, already in 1996, it was shown by Professor Herget's group that alveolar macrophages harvested from the lungs of rats exposed to hypoxia produced more ROS than macrophages from normoxic animals [50]. In addition,

macrophages can digest the ECM with their proteolytic enzymes and may even proliferate in the pathologically altered vascular wall (for a review, see [16,51]). In our experiments, we therefore grew rat aortic VSMCs either in cocultures with rat alveolar macrophages or on a collagen substrate pre-modified with these macrophages activated by TiO₂ dust. We found that macrophages themselves did not proliferate in co-cultures but activated VSMCs to increase proliferation. Because this increased proliferative activity of VSMCs became apparent only after several days of coculture, we reasoned that it was induced by paracrine production of cytokines, chemokines and growth factors by macrophages (for a review, see [52-54]), rather than being an immediate effect of short-living oxygen radicals produced in these cells. A recent study by Professor Herget's followers has shown that alveolar macrophages exposed to hypoxia were able to produce superoxide only *in vivo* but not *in vitro*, although they were able under both conditions to polarize to pro-proliferative M2 macrophages [55]. On collagen modified by activated macrophages, similar to UV light-modified collagen, the cells adhered more weakly, were prone to spontaneous detachment, and showed signs of damage (e.g., vacuolization). The remaining undamaged cells, however, proliferated rapidly and soon compensated for these cell losses [45].

In the context of ROS, it is also worth mentioning the dual role of NO in the pathogenesis of pulmonary hypertension. At relatively low concentrations of ROS, NO exerts vasodilatory and antiproliferative effects on VSMCs. At high ROS concentrations, however, NO gives rise to peroxynitrite, nitrotyrosine, and other highly reactive molecules. Thus, it changes its initial beneficial effect, alleviating pulmonary hypertension, into an effect that further aggravates this hypertension [10,15,25,35,36].

3.2. Effect of proteolytic enzymes and mast cells

Cells of the immune system, infiltrating the vascular wall during hypoxia, also produce proteolytic enzymes such as chymases, tryptases and metalloproteinases (MMPs). These proteolytic enzymes degrade the ECM of pulmonary vessels, especially collagen [36,56,57], and thus are another important factor that induces VSMC proliferation by releasing these cells from growth inhibition by the physiological ECM (for a review, see [47,58]). VSMC proliferation then leads to thickening of the pulmonary vessel walls, increasing their rigidity and peripheral resistance, and thus leads to long-term fixation of pulmonary hypertension. The thickening and the rigidity of pulmonary vessels are further promoted by the increased synthesis of ECM molecules, particularly collagen, by the multiplied VSMCs [16,51].

Among the cells of the immune system, we paid special attention to **mast cells** in our studies. These cells have been relatively little considered in the pathogenesis of hypoxic pulmonary hypertension, and in the pathogenesis of vascular diseases in general. They have even been referred to as "forgotten cells" in the literature, although up to one in five cells of all cell types present in a pathologically altered vessel wall may be a mast cell (for a review, see [59,60]). These cells also play an important role in various fibrotic diseases, such as renal, pulmonary, hepatic and cardiac fibrosis and the formation of hypertrophic scars (for a review, see [61]).

In our studies on the effect of mast cells on VSMC proliferation, we chose **RBL-2H3 cells**, i.e. a rat basophilic leukemia (mastocytoma) cell line, as a model of mast cells infiltrating the walls of pulmonary blood vessels. We first compared the production of proteolytic enzymes in these cells and in cell types present in the vascular wall, such as endothelial cells, VSMCs and fibroblasts. We found that the production of chymases, tryptases and metalloproteinases was several times higher in RBL-2H3 cells than in vascular wall cell types. Moreover, the production of these enzymes was usually higher in RBL-2H3 cells cultured in a hypoxic atmosphere (3% O₂ + 5% CO₂) than in a normoxic

atmosphere (21% O₂ + 5% CO₂), whereas the production of proteolytic enzymes in vascular wall cell types was not affected by hypoxia or was even reduced. However, immunofluorescence staining of MMP-13 revealed that endothelial cells and VSMCs cultured under hypoxic conditions contained more numerous and more brightly stained granules with this enzyme than the cells cultured in normoxia [39,40]. In a follow-up study, we then monitored the growth of VSMCs on type I collagen pre-exposed to RBL-2H3 cells cultivated for 48 hours in **normoxia or hypoxia**. On collagen pre-modified by normoxic RBL-2H3 cells, the proliferation activity of VSMCs was similar to that on unmodified collagen. However, on collagen pre-modified by hypoxic RBL-2H3 cells, the cell population doubling time was significantly shorter, and the final cell population density was significantly higher than on unmodified collagen. This behavior of VSMC was explained by the degradation of collagen by proteases released from RBL-2H3 cells, which was more pronounced in hypoxic RBL-2H3 cells [59]. In addition, mast cells, including RBL-2H3 cells, can produce various chemokines and cytokines, which can stimulate the growth of VSMCs (for a review, see [52]).

We further focused on the adhesion and growth of VSMCs on collagen modified by **primary mast cells** isolated from rat lungs. Type I collagen was deposited in polystyrene culture wells and was exposed for 1 or 3 days to mast cells seeded into the inserts above the collagen and cultured in a normoxic or hypoxic atmosphere. The collagen substrate was then rinsed with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) and was seeded with rat aortic VSMCs (approx. 2150 cells/cm²). In the case of one-day exposure of mast cells to hypoxia, the cell number on collagen pre-modified by hypoxic mast cells was significantly higher than on collagen pre-modified by normoxic cells (**Figure 1A**). In the case of three-day exposure of mast cells to hypoxia, the significant difference in VSMC numbers on collagen modified by mast cells in normoxia and hypoxia disappeared, but the number of VSMCs on collagen modified by normoxic or hypoxic mast cells became significantly higher than on unmodified collagen (**Figure 1B**).

Figure 1. The population density of rat aortic VSMCs on day 3 after seeding on pure polystyrene wells (PS well), on PS wells coated with dry type I collagen (Col), on PS wells coated with type I collagen and pre-wetted with the cell culture medium (Col+DMEM), on type I collagen pre-incubated with primary rat lung mast cells (MC) for 1 day (A) or for 3 days (B), and on type I collagen pre-incubated with MC stimulated with a calcium ionophore A23187 (MC+A23). The preparation of samples before VSMC seeding was done either in normoxia or in hypoxia. Mean \pm SEM from 18 measurements, Student *t*-test for unpaired data. Statistical significance: * $p \leq 0.05$ in comparison with corresponding samples in normoxia, # $p \leq 0.01$ in comparison with Col, \$ $p \leq 0.05$ in comparison with Col+DMEM.

However, a disadvantage of primary cultures of mast cells from rat lungs (by bronchoalveolar lavage) was the frequent presence of bacterial contamination. We therefore performed further studies on **extracts from normoxic and hypoxic mast cells**, containing proteases. The mast cell extracts were prepared using a solution containing 1 part PBS, 1 part 280 mM sorbitol, 1 mM Ca^{2+} and 0.5 mM Mg^{2+} . Collagen type I, deposited on the bottoms of polystyrene culture wells, was exposed to these extracts for 20 hours in a cell incubator, and was then rinsed with PBS and deionized H_2O , dried and seeded with rat aortic VSMCs (approx. 2150 cells/ cm^2). The cells were cultured either in standard Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Minimum Essential Medium (DMEM) with 10% of fetal bovine serum or in a chemically defined serum-free medium supplemented with epidermal growth factor (EGF), fibroblast growth factor (FGF) and insulin (BD Biocoat, Cat. No. 355160), already used in our previous study [40]. The reason was to minimize the adsorption of serum proteins, such as vitronectin, fibronectin, and albumin, which influence cell adhesion and spreading and can mask the effect of the modified collagen on VSMCs.

The advantage of using a serum-free medium was evident on day 1 after cell seeding. It can be seen from **Figure 2A** that the number of cells on 1 day after seeding tended to be highest on collagen modified with hypoxic mast cell extract. However, this difference was not statistically significant in the standard serum-supplemented medium, and only became significant in the serum-free medium, at least when compared to the pure culture dish. The size of the cell spreading area was generally larger in VSMCs on collagen-coated dishes than on uncoated dishes, regardless of collagen modification. However, in the serum-free medium, the cell spreading area was smaller in VSMCs on collagen modified by extracts from mast cells, whether normoxic or hypoxic (**Figure 2B**).

In the following days, VSMCs proliferated on all tested substrates with similar dynamics. However, in a serum-containing medium, the highest cell numbers were achieved on unmodified collagen (**Figure 2 C**), whereas in a serum-free medium (where the adsorption of molecules with a potential masking effect was minimized), the highest cell numbers were achieved on collagen modified with hypoxic mast cell extract (**Figure 2D**).

Figure 2. The number (A) and the spreading area (B) of rat aortic VSMCs on day 1 after seeding on pure polystyrene wells (PS well), on PS wells coated with type I collagen (Col), on PS wells coated with Col exposed to extracts from mast cells cultured under normoxia (Norm) or hypoxia (Hyp) or exposed to the extraction solution (Sol). Mean \pm SEM. from 9-18 measurements (A) or from 34-82 cells, Student *t*-test for unpaired data. Statistical significance: * $p \leq 0.05$ in comparison with PS dish, ** $p \leq 0.01$ and *** $p \leq 0.001$ in comparison with the Col. Growth curves of these VSMCs from day 1 to day 7 (C, D). The cells were cultured either in a standard serum-supplemented medium (DMEM+FBS) or in a serum-free medium.

Among all proteolytic enzymes produced by mast cells, we finally turned most attention to **MMP-13**. This enzyme is an interstitial collagenase, the principal enzyme responsible for the initiation of collagen breakdown in the rat species during the development of hypoxic pulmonary hypertension [38]. We therefore studied the adhesion, growth and viability of VSMC in cultures on collagen I exposed to MMP-13. Collagen I was adsorbed on polystyrene culture dishes, digested with MMP-13, seeded with rat aortic VSMC (approx. 2500 cells/cm²) and incubated in DMEM with 10% of fetal bovine serum (FBS) for 1 to 7 days.

We found that the VSMCs on MMP-13-treated collagen adhered in about 1.5 times lower initial numbers than the cells on unmodified collagen (2200 ± 200 vs. 1490 ± 650 cells/cm²; $p < 0.01$). In addition, these cells were usually less spread, i.e. they contacted the modified collagen by a smaller cell adhesion area. Their shape was often round or spindle-like, whereas the cells on unmodified collagen were mainly polygonal. The concentration of β_1 -integrin adhesion receptors and β -actin in cells on MMP-13-treated collagen was lower by about 35% (**Figure 3**). The concentrations of focal

adhesion proteins talin and vinculin, and a contractile protein α -actin, were unchanged, but the clustering of the first two proteins into focal adhesion plaques, as well as the assembly of α - and β -actin-containing microfilaments, were lower (**Figure 4**). The cells on MMP-13-treated collagen contained more heat-shock protein 60 (by $20 \pm 7\%$), and were more prone to cell death, as indicated by a more than 3 times higher number of trypan blue-stained cells (**Figure 5A**). As a result, the growth curves showed that the cells on MMP-13-modified collagen proliferated more slowly than the cells on the control unmodified collagen. However, the VSMCs on the modified collagen proliferated for a longer period of time, whereas on unmodified collagen the cells reached their maximum population density earlier and entered the stationary phase (**Figure 5B**). These results suggested that the cells on MMP-13-degraded collagen escaped the ECM-mediated growth control more easily and increased their turnover [48,58]. Increased turnover of VSMCs, i.e. coexistence of proliferation and apoptosis, has been shown repeatedly in the pulmonary vascular cells of rats with hypoxic pulmonary hypertension (for a review, see [11]).

Figure 3. Concentration of adhesion molecules (β_1 -integrins, talin, vinculin), cytoskeletal proteins (α -actin, β -actin) and heat-shock proteins 60 and 70 (HSP 60, HSP 70) in rat aortic VSMCs cultured on unmodified collagen I (white columns) and on MMP-13-degraded collagen I (black columns). Measured by ELISA per mg of protein on day 3 after seeding. The absorbances of cell samples from the degraded collagen are expressed as percentages of the values obtained from control cells on unmodified collagen. Mean \pm SEM from 2-4 experiments, Student t-test for unpaired data, * $p < 0.05$ compared to control values.

Figure 4. Immunofluorescence staining of vinculin (A, B), talin (C, D), alpha-actin (E, F) and beta-actin (G, H) in 3-day-old cultures of rat aortic VSMCs grown on unmodified collagen I (A, C, E, G) or on collagen I digested with MMP-13 (B, D, F, H). Zeiss Axioplan epifluorescence microscope, scale bar = 10 μ m.

Figure 5. A. Percentage of trypan blue-stained cells in 2-day-old cultures of rat aortic VSMCs on unmodified collagen I (Col. I), on collagen I digested by MMP-13 (Col. I + 13), on polystyrene tissue culture dishes (PS dish), and on glass coverslips (Glass). Mean \pm SEM from 15 measurements. ** $p < 0.01$ compared to control values on Col. I. **B.** Growth curves of VSMCs on Col. I and Col. I+MMP-13. Mean \pm SEM from 20 measurements (days 1 to 4) or from 4 measurements (days 5 to 7).

3.3. Changes in the ECM of pulmonary arteries *in vivo*

Our further studies on changes in the ECM of pulmonary arteries during hypoxia and their potential influence on the behavior of VSMCs were performed in rats *in vivo*. The rats were exposed to hypoxia (10% O₂) in a normobaric hypoxic chamber for four days. The rats were then euthanized, and pulmonary arteries (approximately 250–400 μ m in diameter, 3rd–5th order, classified as conduit arteries) were subjected to immunohistochemical, proteomic, and real-time PCR analyses, focused particularly on non-fibrillar collagens of type IV and VI [62]. Type IV collagen is located in the basal lamina of cells, including VSMCs, and it helps maintain VSMCs in a differentiated state. Plating VSMCs on type IV collagen induced an increase in contractile proteins, namely α -actin and myosin heavy chain, in these cells. Moreover, various types of stem cells seeded on type IV collagen spontaneously differentiated towards smooth muscle cell phenotype (for a review, see [63]). Type VI collagen is located in the basement membrane and in the interstitium between cells. It has been reported to induce the differentiation of fibroblasts into myofibroblasts, manifested by their expression of smooth muscle α -actin (for a review, see [63]). Type VI collagen consists of three chains (α 1, α 2, and α 3). The α 3(VI) chain is approximately three times longer than the α 1(VI) and α 2(VI) chains and, unlike the other chains, contains a Kunitz-like terminal domain (C5). This C5 domain, after cleavage from the α 3(VI) main chain, represents a biologically active peptide, endotrophin [64,65]. Endotrophin appears to be one of the key players in the signaling effects mediated by collagen VI, including its pro-fibrotic nature and macrophage chemoattractant [66].

We found that the expression of type IV collagen in the *tunica media* of arteries of hypoxia-exposed rats was not changed at protein and mRNA levels. However, type VI collagen was significantly reduced in the *tunica media* of hypoxic rats at protein level (Figure 6), while its expression at mRNA level increased. In our study [62], this phenomenon was described for the first time. At the same time, we detected a significant increase in MMP-9 in the *tunica media*, while the

expression of MMP-2 at both protein and mRNA levels was decreased in the *tunica media*. We concluded that the loss of collagen VI and increasing concentration of endotrophin could be important factors inducing the phenotypic modulation of VSMCs, i.e., loss of their contractile filaments (e.g., α -actin-containing) and activating their migration and proliferation, which leads to remodeling of the pulmonary arteries during hypoxic pulmonary hypertension. At the same time, collagen VI was retained in the *tunica adventitia*, which could promote the differentiation of adventitial fibroblasts to myofibroblasts [62].

Figure 6. A significant decrease in the content of collagen VI (red lines with black dots: collagen VI forms this type of "beady" fibrils) in the tunica media of pulmonary arteries (about 300 μm in diameter) during hypoxia. At the same time, the amount of type IV collagen (green on the surface of the VSMCs) remained unchanged. Fibrillar collagens (type I and III) are drawn in black, and collagen VI anchors them to collagen IV. A biologically active peptide, endotrophin, cleaved from the $\alpha3(VI)$ is drawn in blue. The status of some VSMCs changes during the development of HPH (decreasing concentration of the protein myosin 11, a marker of the differentiated status of VSMCs). Modified from [62].

3.4. The effect of hypoxia on the growth of VSMCs

The pulmonary arteries mentioned above (approximately 250–400 μm in diameter, 3rd–5th order), were also used for isolation of VSMCs in our experiments. The arteries were dissected from the lungs of normoxic and hypoxic rats under a microscope, were visually cleared of *tunica adventitia*, and were minced into fragments (0.5 mm³ or less). These fragments were digested by collagenase, and VSMCs were isolated from them by an explantation method [47,67]. The identity of the VSMCs was verified by smooth muscle α -actin detection at protein level [62]. The cells were then cultured in a humidified air atmosphere either under normoxic conditions (21% O₂ and 5% CO₂) or under hypoxic conditions, (2.5% O₂ and 5% CO₂). The growth of four experimental groups of cells was compared:

- VSMCs from hypoxic rats cultured in a hypoxic atmosphere ("hypox in hypox"),
- VSMCs from hypoxic rats cultured in a normoxic atmosphere ("hypox in normox"),

- (c) VSMCs from normoxic rats cultured in a hypoxic atmosphere, (“normox in hypox”)
- (d) VSMCs from normoxic rats cultured in a normoxic atmosphere (“normox in normox”).

We found that the proliferation activity tended to be highest in group (a) and lowest in group (d) (**Figure 7**). Although these differences were not statistically significant, this result is consistent with our earlier findings of increased VSMC growth on collagen modified by hypoxic mast cells (**Figures 1 and 2**). This result is also consistent with earlier studies by other authors, who described an increased proliferative activity of VSMCs of pulmonary arteries in HPH in humans and in various laboratory animals, such as mice, rats and calves (for a review, see [11,49]). It is also evident that culturing cells from hypoxic donors in normoxia tended to attenuate the proliferative activity of VSMCs, whereas culturing cells from normoxic donors in hypoxia enhanced this activity, although not to the level of the activity of hypoxic cells cultured in hypoxia (**Figure 7**).

Figure 7. Number of VSMCs isolated from pulmonary arteries of hypoxic and normoxic rats after 1, 3 or 7 days of cultivation in a hypoxic or normoxic atmosphere. Mean \pm SD, $n = 5$. One Way ANOVA, Student-Newman-Keuls Method, $p \leq 0.05$. No statistically significant difference was detected.

3.5. The role of hypoxia-inducible factors in vascular remodeling

In addition to the effect of ROS and ECM degradation, investigated in our earlier studies, hypoxia-inducible factors (HIFs) play another important role in the stimulation of VSMC proliferation and vascular remodeling during HPH. HIFs are oxygen-sensitive transcription factors governing the metabolic response of cells to low oxygen levels. There are three basic members of the human HIF family, namely HIF-1, HIF-2 and HIF-3. HIFs are heterodimers composed of oxygen-sensitive α subunit (HIF-1 α , HIF-2 α , HIF-3 α) and oxygen-insensitive β subunit (HIF-1 β , HIF-2 β , HIF-3 β) [11]. HIF-1 α is primarily expressed in VSMCs, HIF-2 α is predominantly found in endothelial cells (although its role in VSMC should not be underestimated), and HIF-3 α is predominantly expressed in pulmonary fibroblasts [68]. The interplay between all members of the HIF family then leads to the onset and development of HPH with all its phases, i.e. from pulmonary vasoconstriction to vascular remodeling.

HIFs are responsible for the activation of more than 2% of human genes participating in the cellular adaptive response in order to maintain oxygen homeostasis [11,41,68]. Erythropoietin was the first

of the genes for which the HIF regulation was described (by HIF-1 α), and in this way pharmacological interference with the HIF system was investigated as a possible therapy for anemia. Professor Herget's followers focused on roxadustat, a prolyl hydroxylase inhibitor and HIF stabilizer [69]. It is known that HIFs promote VSMC contraction by inhibiting K⁺ channels, which leads to the influx of Ca²⁺ ions [11,68]. The application of roxadustat can therefore be associated with a risk of increased pulmonary vascular resistance and vasoconstrictor reactivity. Fortunately, this risk was not confirmed when roxadustat was administered to rats for 14 days. However, this risk should be taken into account, since HIFs and their stabilizers or activators can support blood vessel remodeling [69]. Calcium ions entering the VSMCs can stimulate their proliferation, especially in combination with the shift from oxidative phosphorylation to oxygen-independent glycolysis, which likens the behavior of VSMCs to that of tumor cells [11,46,53,68]. HIFs also up-regulate growth factors/receptor tyrosine kinases, activate protein kinase B (AKT) and extracellular signal-regulated kinase (ERK), and mammalian target of rapamycin (mTOR), i.e. factors that promote cell proliferation and survival, and suppress growth inhibitory factors such as phosphatase and tensin homolog (PTEN), p53 and the Hippo signaling pathway [11,68].

Last but not least, HIF-1 α increases the expression of CD146, which is a co-receptor of vascular endothelial growth factor receptor 2 (VEGFR2) and platelet-derived growth factor receptor- β (PDGFR- β), and further enhances the expression of HIF-1 α [11,68,70]. In this context, it is interesting to recall that VEGF and PDGF are hypoxia-inducible growth factors, which stimulate the migration and proliferation of VSMCs [41]. Ultimately, HIFs in VSMCs stimulate a switch from the quiescent contractile phenotype to a synthetic and proliferative phenotype, inhibit VSMC apoptosis, and also induce osteogenic differentiation of VSMCs, which results in blood vessel calcification [11,68]. VSMCs also acquire a pro-inflammatory phenotype, characterized by the expression of cell adhesion molecules of the immunoglobulin and selectin families, and by the production of various chemokines, cytokines and growth factors, attracting cells of the immune system (e.g. monocytes, macrophages, lymphocytes) and promoting their proliferation [11,16,49,51].

It can be summarized that HIF-1 plays a major role in driving vasoconstriction and VSMC proliferation, while HIF-2 plays a major role in inflammatory cell recruitment via activation of endothelial cells and VSMCs to a pro-inflammatory phenotype. HIF-2 α is therefore considered to play a major role in the initiation of HPH, whereas HIF-1 α may play a major role in the progression and perpetuation of the disease [71].

3.6. The role of miRNA in vascular remodeling

Other important factors in the onset and development of HPH, including vascular remodeling, are microRNAs (miRNAs). These molecules are single-stranded small noncoding RNAs (18–22 nt in length) that can directly degrade or repress the translation of their target mRNAs, thus negatively regulating gene expression at the posttranscriptional level [52,72]. As it is estimated that at least 30% of genes in the human genome are directly regulated by miRNAs, a growing number of studies are revealing that miRNAs play a unique and pivotal role in the progression of HPH through the phenotypic switch of VSMCs from a contractile to a synthetic phenotype. The non-proliferative differentiated contractile phenotype is characterized by the expression of myocardin, α -actin, SM22 α (early markers of VSMC differentiation), h-caldesmon and calponin-1 (intermediate markers of VSMC differentiation) and desmin, meta-vinculin, SM1 and the SM2 isoforms of myosin heavy chain and smoothelin (late markers of VSMC differentiation). During the transition to the synthetic phenotype, these markers are gradually lost, in order from late to early, so that some level of the early markers, e.g. α -actin, is retained by cells in the synthetic phenotype (for a review, see [49,51]). In

addition, some isoforms of differentiation markers are replaced by others, e.g. α -actin by β -actin or SM1 and SM2 isoforms of myosin heavy chain by myosin heavy chain embryonic (SMemb). Other markers of synthetic VSMCs include the presence of tropomyosin 4, increased synthesis of ECM proteins and glycoproteins, such as collagen and osteopontin-8, and particularly increased migration and proliferation activity [72]. The transition from the contractile to the synthetic phenotype and *vice versa* is regulated by specific miRNAs that ultimately either stimulate VSMC proliferation or have an antiproliferative effect (**Table 2**), and modulation of their expression could therefore be used in the prevention and therapy of HPH.

Table 2. *MicroRNAs which promote or inhibit the switch from contractile to synthetic phenotype and proliferation of VSMCs in HPH.*

Dependence/effect	Pro-proliferative	Anti-proliferative	Reference
Hypoxia-dependent	miRNA-9 miRNA-20a miRNA-23a miRNA-214	miRNA-17~92 cluster miRNA-30c miRNA-124 miRNA-140 miRNA-206 miRNA-449	[72]
	miRNA-17 miRNA-18a-5p miRNA-19a miRNA-92b-3 miRNA-143 miRNA-145 miRNA-155-5p miRNA-214 miRNA-1260b	miRNA-26b-5p miRNA-140-5p miRNA-150 miRNA-223 miRNA-760	[52]
Growth factor-dependent	miRNA-221 miRNA-15b miRNA-96 miRNA-24	miRNA-21 miRNA-132	[72]

3.7. Cell types other than VSMC in vascular remodeling

During HPH, a metabolically reprogrammed, proliferative, and pro-inflammatory phenotype is acquired not only by VSMCs but also by other cell types present in the blood vessel wall. These cells include intimal endothelial cells and adventitial fibroblasts, which can be considered as “sentinel cells” separating VSMCs from the blood and the surrounding vascular environment, and which are activated first in response to various adverse factors [16,42,46,53]. Endothelial cells can produce endothelin-1, a potent vasoconstrictor, which stimulates the expression of HIF-1 α in VSMCs, promotes the proliferation of VSMCs and fibroblasts, and facilitates the production of ECM by these cells [14,68]. Moreover, endothelial cells can undergo a so-called endothelial-to-mesenchymal transition and acquire a VSMC-like phenotype, characterized by the presence of smooth muscle α -actin [71]. A similar transformation can be observed in adventitial fibroblasts, which transform into myofibroblasts positive for smooth muscle α -actin, and resemble VSMCs [15,16,41,49]. These fibroblasts are capable of proliferating, stimulating the proliferation of VSMCs, and particularly recruiting monocytes and lymphocytes (e.g., T-cells) and activating them into cells with the pro-inflammatory and pro-remodeling phenotype [16,73,74]. Last but not least, VSMC-like cells capable of proliferation and paracrine secretion of growth factors can arise from progenitor cells, either

resident in the vascular wall or circulating in the blood after their release from the bone marrow [15,49].

3.8. Markers of VSMC differentiation in HPH

Interesting results were obtained when the expression of genes for markers of VSMC differentiation was studied at mRNA level by real-time qPCR in VSMC isolated from pulmonary arteries of hypoxic rats. These markers included smooth muscle α -actin, calponin-1 and myosin heavy chain, i.e. early, intermediate and late markers of VSMC differentiation, respectively (for a review, see [49,51,72]). We expected a loss in the mRNA expression of these markers as a sign of phenotypic modulation of VSMCs during HPH. However, the expression of α -actin was unchanged in hypoxic VSMCs, and the expression of **calponin-1** and particularly **myosin heavy chain** was even increased (**Figure 8**). At the same time, the expression of type I collagen was unchanged, but the cells from hypoxic rats showed an increased expression of **galectin-3**. This β -galactosyl-binding protein, considered to be implicated in the pathogenesis of HPH, can have a **dual effect** on VSMCs. On the one hand, an increased expression of Gal-3 in VSMCs was reported to be associated with increased proliferation activity of these cells and their lower tendency to apoptosis [75]. Moreover, in VSMCs, Gal-3 induced the expression of osteopontin, a marker of phenotypic modulation of VSMCs towards synthetic phenotype, associated with VSMC proliferation and vascular calcification [76]. On the other hand, Gal-3 was reported to stimulate cell differentiation towards contractile VSMC phenotype, e.g. by inducing the expression of α -actin in endothelial cells [77] and by increasing the expression of α -actin and calponin in VSMCs [76]. This is probably related to the pro-fibrotic effect of Gal-3, as α -actin and calponin can also be considered as markers of fibrosis [78].

Figure 8. Expression of genes encoding α -actin (ACTA2), myosin heavy chain (MYH11), calponin-1 (CNN1), type I collagen (COL1A1) and galectin-3 (LGALS3) in VSMCs isolated from pulmonary arteries of normoxic and hypoxic rats (passage 2) and cultivated for 6 days in a normoxic atmosphere and in a hypoxic atmosphere, respectively. Mean + SD, n = 5. Student's t-test, $p \leq 0.05$. * significant difference compared to normoxic cells.

Hypoxia may also have a **dual effect** on the differentiation status of VSMCs. On the one hand, as already explained, it promotes the dedifferentiation of initially contractile VSMCs into a synthetic phenotype, but on the other hand, it is used to differentiate stem cells into different cell types, such

as endothelial cells [79,80], chondrocytes [81], osteoblasts [82], cardiomyocytes (for a review, see [83]), and also smooth muscle cells. For example, in a recent study by [84], human subcutaneous adipose tissue-derived stem cells (ADSCs), cultivated in an induction medium containing transforming growth factor beta-1 (TGF- β 1) and bone morphogenetic protein-4 (BMP-4) and subjected to hypoxia (1% of O₂), increased the expression of α -actin, SM22 α , calponin, and myosin heavy chain, i.e. markers of VSMC differentiation, which was mediated by N6-adenosine methyltransferases (Mettl3). At the same time, however, hypoxia and Mettl3 induced paracrine production of VEGF, TGF- β , hepatocyte growth factor (HGF), granulocyte-macrophage colony-stimulating factor (GM-CSF), basic fibroblast growth factor (bFGF), and stromal cell-derived factor-1 (SDF-1), i.e. factors promoting not only the differentiation but also the proliferation of ADSCs [84].

Therefore, the described dual effects of Gal-3 expression and hypoxia, i.e., these two opposing tendencies in the maintenance of the differentiated state of VSMCs, may meet in our studies. Moreover, the growth effect of both these factors may not only be **cell hyperplasia** but also **cell hypertrophy**.

3.9. The question of VSMC hypertrophy in HPH

Figure 9 clearly shows that in cultures of VSMCs isolated from the pulmonary arteries of hypoxic rats, more cells are spread over a larger area on the cultivation substrate than in the case of VSMCs from normoxic arteries, which may indicate their larger volume. This distinctly larger area is evident not only on the culture polystyrene but also on various ECM proteins present in the vascular wall, such as collagen I, IV, VI, and fibronectin (**Figure 10**), and not only when the cells from hypoxic rats were cultured under hypoxia (**Figure 9**), but also when they were cultured under normoxia (“hypox in normox”; **Figure 10**).

Figure 9. Morphology of VSMCs isolated from pulmonary arteries of normoxic (**A, B**) and hypoxic (**C, D**) rats and cultivated for 1 day (**A, C**) and for 4 days (**B, D**) in DMEM with 10% of FBS in a normoxic atmosphere (**A, B**) and in a hypoxic atmosphere (**C, D**). F-actin in the cells was stained with phalloidin conjugated with TRITC, cell nuclei were counterstained with Hoechst 33342. Olympus IX 71 microscope, DP 70 digital camera. Scale bar represents 100 μm .

Figure 10. Morphology of VSMCs isolated from pulmonary arteries of normoxic (A, C, E, G) and hypoxic (B, D, F, H) rats and cultivated for 4 days in pure polystyrene wells (A, B), in wells coated with type I collagen (C, D), with type IV collagen (E, F) or with type VI collagen (G, H). Cells stained

with Texas Red C₂ maleimide. Olympus IX 51 microscope, DP 70 digital camera, obj. 10x. Scale bar represents 100 μ m.

Hypertrophy and strengthening of the contractile apparatus of VSMCs may result from their increased mechanical stress in hypertension. In the vessels of the systemic circulation, this hypertrophy may also be associated with polyploidy of the cells. This polyploidy is the result of incomplete growth stimulation, which leads to DNA synthesis and mitosis of cells that are not followed by karyokinesis of the cells, or at least their cytokinesis, which also leads to the formation of binucleated cells. This process is also referred to as endoreduplication [85]. VSMCs with duplicated or multiplied chromosomal equipment are then considered to be more efficient in the synthesis of contractile and ECM proteins, and thus better able to withstand an increased mechanical load. In this sense, hypertrophy and polyploidization of cells are considered a kind of differentiation of VSMCs [67]; for a review, see [51]). Another mechanism of possible polyploidy in pulmonary hypertension could be cell fusion initiated by circulating cells that contribute to tissue repair [86]. However, the presence of polyploidy in pulmonary vessels is rather unlikely, as shown by studies based on flow cytometry [87] or based on fluorescent *in situ* hybridization (FISH; [86]).

However, cell hypertrophy can also be a sign of cell senescence. Studies by Born *et al.* have shown that HPH was associated with the accumulation of senescent VSMC, and also endothelial cells, mainly at sites of vascular hypertrophy. This accumulation coincided with increases in the DNA damage markers gamma H2A histone family member X (γ -H2AX) and tumor suppressor p53 binding protein 1 (53BP1). Senescent VSMCs stimulated the migration and growth of neighboring cells through the secretion of paracrine factors, whereas senescent endothelial cells released pro-inflammatory factors attracting cells of the immune system. Nevertheless, the elimination of senescent cells by senolytic therapies aggravated pulmonary hypertension, which resulted mainly from the removal of senescent endothelial cells and further activation of VSMC proliferation and loss of lung capillaries (for a review, see [88]). Senescent cells with reduced proliferative capacity have been demonstrated in pulmonary arteries during HPH in studies by the group of Stenmark *et al.* Their occurrence depended on the duration and severity of hypoxia, the duration of hypertension, and the localization in the pulmonary circulation, where they varied in the length and thickness of the vessels (for a review, see [49]).

4. Treatment options for HPH

Although the causes and mechanisms of the pathogenesis of HPH have been intensively investigated and are relatively well-understood, effective treatment of this disease, which would also minimize adverse side effects, still remains an important subject for further research. The treatment of HPH depends on the level at which oxygen delivery to the lungs is impaired. If the ambient oxygen content is reduced, for example during acute or chronic mountain sickness occurring at high altitudes, direct **inhalation of oxygen** may be recommended.

Current treatment of pulmonary hypertension focuses on endothelial dysfunction, which is affected by **three key pathways**, namely the **prostacyclin**, **endothelin** and **NO** pathways [89].

Prostacyclin binds to the PGI₂ receptor and leads to smooth muscle relaxation and pulmonary artery vasodilation. Products include Epoprostenol and Treprostinil for i.v. administration (short half-life), inhalable Iloprost, orally active stable Beraprost and the prostacyclin receptor agonist Selexiopag [89].

The **endothelin pathway** focuses on the inhibition of vasoconstriction and VSMC proliferation (endothelin A receptor), NO and prostacyclin production (endothelin B receptor). An oral dual receptor antagonist is Bosentan [12,90].

Nitric oxide is produced and released by vascular endothelial cells. **Inhaled NO** acts as a selective pulmonary vasodilator, and it is currently approved by the FDA for the treatment of persistent pulmonary hypertension of the newborn. Its benefit was also suggested in its recent application in the scenario of the COVID-19 pandemic [91,92].

However, it must be taken into account that direct inhalation of both oxygen and NO is associated with a risk of oxidative stress to the tissues, including pulmonary blood vessels, which would be counterproductive [91,92]. Moreover, inhaled NO can have a negative feedback on endogenous NO production. Thus, instead of direct inhalation of NO, infusion of **L-arginine**, which is used by NO synthase as a substrate, can be recommended [90], or indirect stimulation of NO action by **phosphodiesterase-5 (PDE5) inhibitors**, e.g., Sildenafil, Tadalafil, and Vardenafil [31]. However, PDE5 inhibitors appear to have clear beneficial effects in pulmonary hypertension of group 1, i.e. pulmonary arterial hypertension (PAH), while they may not improve the condition of patients in the non-PAH groups 2 to 5, i.e., including group 3, HPH [12,31]. If HPH is a consequence of lung disease, the underlying disease should be treated first, for example with bronchodilators in COPD, anti-inflammatory drugs and antifibrotics (Pirfenidone) in interstitial lung diseases, or nocturnal positive pressure therapy in obstructive sleep apnea syndrome [12].

Current therapy for pulmonary hypertension focuses mainly on dilating pulmonary blood vessels; new approaches include suppressing cell proliferation and inflammation. Drugs for already-known targets are **tyrosine kinase inhibitors** (Imatinib), **Rho-kinase inhibitors** (Fasudil) [93,94], **serotonin receptor antagonists** (Terguride) or **interleukin 6 (IL6) receptor antagonists** (Tocilizumab).

Some drugs that have been shown to be effective in PAH can also be used to treat HPH. Compared to HPH, the pathogenesis of PAH is more complex and involves a wide range of different mechanisms, such as the role of inflammation and immunity, mitochondrial dysfunction, oxidative stress, extracellular matrix, metabolism, neurohumoral modulation, estrogen signaling pathway, DNA damage, etc. [95]. PAH has a genetic component, mutations in bone morphogenetic protein receptor 2 (BMPR-II). However, BMPR-II may be a target for treatment not only of hereditary PAH but also of HPH, where it reverses vascular remodeling [4].

Other effective therapeutic interventions against vascular remodeling could include silencing or enhancing the **specific miRNAs** mentioned above (**Table 2**; [52,72]), or silencing the expression of HIFs by **small interfering RNAs (siRNAs)**. Other important **inhibitors of HIFs** include natural, mostly plant-derived compounds such as resveratrol, a stilbene polyphenol with antioxidant, cardioprotective, anti-inflammatory, anticancer and anti-HPH effects, chrysin (a flavonoid compound), tetramethylpyrazine, *Lycium barbarum* polysaccharides, phytoestrogens, genistein, and others [71,96]. Other well-known natural antioxidant and anti-inflammatory agents derived from plants are the phenolic compounds curcumin and quercetin [97].

AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK) also plays an important role in antioxidant, antiproliferative, and antihypertrophic pathways in the pulmonary arteries in HPH. Thus, activation of AMPK is another potential therapeutic target for HPH. The AMPK activators are pharmacological, such as metformin, 5-aminoimidazole-4-carboxamide ribonucleotide (AICAR) or statins, phytochemical, such as resveratrol, or adipokines, e.g. adiponectin [98].

Statins, e.g. simvastatin, are another important group of drugs for the therapy of HPH, primarily intended to reduce cardiovascular risks by lowering the level of blood cholesterol. The mechanisms of this effect seem to include restoration of NO synthase expression and/or activity. Moreover, in the combination of statins with PDE5 inhibitors, the two types of drugs potentiate each other [11,30].

Ion channel modulators are also used in the treatment of HPH. An important example is **dehydroepiandrosterone** (DHEA), a naturally occurring cholesterol-derived steroid hormone, which activates Ca²⁺-gated K⁺ channels mediating vasodilation in the pulmonary circulation and inhibits L-type voltage-gated Ca²⁺ channels, stimulating vasoconstriction [30].

Last but not least, newly-developed therapies include **galectin-3 antagonists** based on oligosaccharide ligands to Gal-3, such as LacNAc (Gal1,4GlcNAc), LacdiNAc (GalNAc1,4GlcNAc) [99] or newly developed glycopolymer inhibitors of Gal-3 based on a polyoxazoline chain decorated with lactosyl or coumaryllactosyl ligands [100].

5. Conclusion and further perspectives

This review article has focused on the history of more than twenty years of collaboration between a group of scientists at the Institute of Physiology of the Czech Academy of Sciences, and Professor Jan Herget's group at the 2nd Faculty of Medicine, and was written to mark the five-year anniversary of his death. The collaboration concerned hypoxic pulmonary hypertension (HPH), and in particular the role of vascular smooth muscle cells (VSMCs) in the onset and development of this disease. The knowledge gained in this collaboration is discussed in the context of world science. HPH belongs to group 3 of pulmonary hypertension, and is caused either by a lack of oxygen in the atmosphere (at high altitudes or in an experimental hypoxic chamber) or by obstructions in the airways themselves, such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, obstructive sleep apnea syndrome, and interstitial pulmonary fibrosis. The immediate response of VSMCs to hypoxia is vasoconstriction, which is reversible but, with prolonged or repeated hypoxia, vascular wall remodeling can occur when migration, proliferation, and phenotypic modulation of VSMCs and other cell types present in the vascular wall, such as endothelial cells and adventitial fibroblasts, are activated. In this activation, an important role is played by reactive oxygen and nitrogen species, by the presence of pro-inflammatory cells (macrophages, mast cells), by degradation of the extracellular matrix by proteases and qualitative changes in its composition, by the production of hypoxia-inducible factors, by changes in the expression of specific micro RNAs, and also by the expression of galectins (galectin-3). Newly-developed treatments for HPH should therefore target the mentioned factors. Our results show that hypoxia has a dual effect on the growth of VSMCs. On the one hand, it promotes their proliferation and hyperplasia; on the other hand, it also promotes the hypertrophy of VSMCs and the expression of contractile proteins in these cells, such as calponin-1 and myosin heavy chain, which seems to be related to the pro-fibrotic effect of hypoxia. This dual effect of hypoxia on VSMC growth in terms of hyperplasia and hypertrophy needs to be further investigated.

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Abbreviations

53BP1, tumor suppressor p53 binding protein 1; **A23**, calcium ionophore A23187; **ACTA2**, actin alpha 2 (an actin protein also referred to as alpha-actin, alpha-actin-2, aortic smooth muscle or alpha-smooth muscle actin (α -SMA, SMactin, alpha-SM-actin, ASMA)); **ADSC(s)**, adipose tissue-derived stem cell(s); **AICAR**, 5-aminoimidazole-4-carboxamide ribonucleotide; **AKT**, alpha serine/threonine-protein kinase, protein kinase B; **AMPK**, AMP-activated protein kinase; **ANOVA**, Analysis of Variance; **Bcl-2**, B cell lymphoma-2; **bFGF**, basic fibroblast growth factor (also known as FGF-2); **BMP-4**, bone morphogenetic protein-4; **BMPR-II**, bone morphogenetic protein receptor 2; **CD146**, cluster of differentiation 146, also known as the melanoma cell adhesion molecule (MCAM) or cell surface glycoprotein MUC18; **CNN1**, gene encoding calponin-1; **Col**, collagen; **COL1A1**, gene encoding collagen type I alpha 1; **COPD**, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; **COVID-19**, coronavirus disease 2019; **CTEPH**, chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension; **DHEA**, dehydroepiandrosterone; **DMEM**, Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Minimum Essential Medium; **DNA**, deoxyribonucleic acid; **ECM**, extracellular matrix; **EGF**, epidermal growth factor; **ELISA**, enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay; **ERK**, extracellular signal-regulated kinase; **ERS**, European Respiratory Society; **ESC**, European Society of Cardiology; **FISH**, fluorescent *in situ* hybridization; **FBS**, fetal bovine serum; **FDA**, U.S. Food and Drug Administration; **FGF**, fibroblast growth factor; **Gal-3**, galectin-3; **γ -H2AX**, gamma H2A histone family member X; **GM-CSF**, granulocyte-macrophage colony-stimulating factor; **HGF**, hepatocyte growth factor; **HIF(s)**, hypoxia-inducible factor(s); **HPH**, hypoxic pulmonary hypertension; **HSP**, heat-shock protein; **Hyp**, hypoxia; **Hypox**, hypoxia; **ICAM-1**, intercellular cell adhesion molecule-1; **IL6**, interleukin 6; **LacdiNAc**, IUPAC name: N-[(2S,3R,4R,5R,6R)-2-[[[(2R,3S,4R,5R)-5-acetamido-4,6-dihydroxy-2-(hydroxymethyl)oxan-3-yl]oxy]-4,5-dihydroxy-6-(hydroxymethyl)oxan-3-yl]acetamide; **LacNAc**, N-Acetyllactosamine, IUPAC name: N-[[β -D-Galactopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 4)-(2-deoxy-D-glucos-2-yl)]acetamide; **LGALS3**, gene encoding human galectin-3; **MAPK**, mitogen-activated protein kinase; **Mettl3**, Methyltransferase 3 (N6-Adenosine-Methyltransferase Complex Catalytic Subunit); **MC**, mast cells; **miRNA(s)**, micro ribonucleic acid(s); **MMP(s)**, metalloproteinase(s); **mTOR**, mammalian target of rapamycin; **mPAP**, mean pulmonary artery pressure; **mPAP/CO**, mean pulmonary arterial pressure to cardiac output; **mRNA**, messenger ribonucleic acid; **MYH11**, Myosin Heavy Chain 11 (a gene encoding myosin-11 protein, also referred to as AAT4, FAA4, SMHC, SMMHC, myosin, heavy chain 11, smooth muscle, myosin heavy chain 11, VSCM2, SMMS-1); **NADPH**, nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate; **NF- κ B**, nuclear factor kappa-light-chain-enhancer of activated B cells; **NO**, nitric oxide; **Norm**, normoxia; **Normox**, normoxia; **nt**, nucleotide; **p**, probability under the null hypothesis of obtaining a real-valued test statistic at least as extreme as the one obtained; **p53**, Tumor protein P53, cellular tumor antigen p53 (UniProt name), or transformation-related protein 53 (TRP53), a regulatory protein that is often mutated in human cancers; **PAH**, pulmonary arterial hypertension; **PAWP**, pulmonary arterial wedge pressure; **PBS**, phosphate-buffered saline; **PCR**, polymerase chain reaction; **PDE5**, phosphodiesterase-5; **PDGF**, platelet-derived growth factor; **PDGFR- β** , platelet-derived growth factor receptor- β ; **PGI2**, prostaglandin I2, also known as prostacyclin; **PH**, pulmonary hypertension; **PS**, polystyrene; **PTEN**, phosphatase and tensin homolog; **PVR**, pulmonary vascular resistance; **qPCR**, quantitative polymerase chain reaction; **RBL-2H3**, a subline of rat basophilic leukemia cells; **RNAs**, ribonucleic acid(s); **ROS**, reactive oxygen species; **SEM**, Standard Error of the Mean; **SD**, Standard Deviation; **SDF-1**, stromal cell-derived factor-1; **Sol**, solution; **SM1**, **SM2**, smooth muscle myosin of SM1 and

SM2 isoforms; **SM22 α** , Smooth Muscle 22 α , a marker of adult smooth muscle; **SMC(s)**, smooth muscle cell(s); **siRNA(s)**, small interfering RNA(s); **SMem β** , smooth muscle myosin heavy chain embryonic; **TGF- β (1)**, transforming growth factor beta(-1); **TRITC**, tetramethylrhodamine isothiocyanate; **UV**, ultraviolet; **VCAM-1**, and vascular cell adhesion molecule-1; **VEGF**, vascular endothelial growth factor; **VEGFR2**, vascular endothelial growth factor receptor 2; *vs.*, *versus*; **VSMC(s)**, vascular smooth muscle cell(s); **WU**, Wood units

References

1. Humbert M, Kovacs G, Hoeper MM, Badagliacca R, Berger RMF, Brida M, Carlsen J, Coats AJS, Escribano-Subias P, Ferrari P, Ferreira DS, Ghofrani HA, Giannakoulas G, Kiely DG, Mayer E, Meszaros G, Nagavci B, Olsson KM, Pepke-Zaba J, Quint JK, Rådegran G, Simonneau G, Sitbon O, Tonia T, Toshner M, Vachiery JL, Noordegraaf AV, Delcroix M, Rosenkranz S, Grp EESD. 2022 ESC/ERS Guidelines for the diagnosis and treatment of pulmonary hypertension. *Eur Respir J* 2023;61:2200879.
2. Vonk Noordegraaf A, Groeneveldt JA, Bogaard HJ. Pulmonary hypertension. *Eur Respir Rev* 2016;25:4-11.
3. Hoeper MM, Ghofrani HA, Grünig E, Klose H, Olschewski H, Rosenkranz S. Pulmonary Hypertension. *Dtsch Arztebl Int* 2017;114:73-84.
4. Thompson AAR, Lawrie A. Targeting Vascular Remodeling to Treat Pulmonary Arterial Hypertension. *Trends Mol Med* 2017;23:31-45.
5. Siddiqui NA, Charoenpong P. Updated 31 July 2023. Pulmonary Veno-Occlusive Disease. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing. Accessed 22 April 2024. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK585129/>
6. Hansmann G. Pulmonary Hypertension in Infants, Children, and Young Adults. *J Am Coll Cardiol* 2017;69:2551-2569.
7. Lichtblau M, Titz A, Bahrampoori B, Schmiedeskamp M, Ulrich S. What changed after the 2022 guidelines for pulmonary hypertension? *Eur J Intern Med* 2023;118:1-5.
8. Thenappan T, Ormiston ML, Ryan JJ, Archer SL. Pulmonary arterial hypertension: pathogenesis and clinical management. *BMJ* 2018;360:j5492.
9. Simonneau G, Montani D, Celermajer DS, Denton CP, Gatzoulis MA, Krowka M, Williams PG, Souza R. Haemodynamic definitions and updated clinical classification of pulmonary hypertension. *Eur Respir J* 2019;53:1801913.
10. Siques P, Pena E, Brito J, El Alam S. Oxidative Stress, Kinase Activation, and Inflammatory Pathways Involved in Effects on Smooth Muscle Cells During Pulmonary Artery Hypertension Under Hypobaric Hypoxia Exposure. *Front Physiol* 2021;12:690341.
11. Chai T, Qiu C, Xian Z, Lu Y, Zeng Y, Li J. A narrative review of research advances in hypoxic pulmonary hypertension. *Ann Transl Med* 2022;10:230.
12. Singh N, Dorfmüller P, Shlobin OA, Ventetuolo CE. Group 3 Pulmonary Hypertension: From Bench to Bedside. *Circ Res* 2022;130:1404-1422.
13. Maimaitiaili N, Zeng Y, Ju P, Zhakeer G, Guangxi E, Yao H, Shi Y, Zhai M, Zhuang J, Peng W, Zhuoga D, Yu Q. NLRC3 deficiency promotes hypoxia-induced pulmonary hypertension development via IKK/NF- κ B p65/HIF-1 α pathway. *Exp Cell Res* 2023;431:113755.
14. Zhang Y, Xu CB. The roles of endothelin and its receptors in cigarette smoke-associated pulmonary hypertension with chronic lung disease. *Pathol Res Pract* 2020;216:153083.
15. Karnati S, Seimetz M, Kleefeldt F, Sonawane A, Madhusudhan T, Bachhuka A, Kosanovic D, Weissmann N, Krüger K, Ergün S. Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease and the Cardiovascular System: Vascular Repair and Regeneration as a Therapeutic Target. *Front Cardiovasc Med* 2021;8:649512.

16. Pugliese SC, Poth JM, Fini MA, Olschewski A, El Kasmi KC, Stenmark KR. The role of inflammation in hypoxic pulmonary hypertension: from cellular mechanisms to clinical phenotypes. *Am J Physiol Lung Cell Mol Physiol* 2015;308:L229-L252.
17. Mandras SA, Mehta HS, Vaidya A. Pulmonary Hypertension: A Brief Guide for Clinicians. *Mayo Clin Proc* 2020;95:1978-1988.
18. Suggett AJ, Herget J. Effect of alpha-methyldopa on the pulmonary vascular changes induced by chronic hypoxia in rats. *Clin Sci Mol Med* 1977;53:397-400.
19. Herget J, Kuklík V. Perinatal lung injury extends in adults the site of hypoxic pulmonary vasoconstriction upstream. *Physiol Res* 1995;44:25-30.
20. Herget J, Paleček F, Vízek M, Holusa R. Causes of experimental pulmonary hypertension in rats. *Physiol Bohemoslov* 1976;25:411-418.
21. Herget J, Paleček F, Preclík P, Čermáková M, Vízek M, Petrovická M. Pulmonary hypertension induced by repeated pulmonary inflammation in the rat. *J Appl Physiol Respir Environ Exerc Physiol* 1981;51:755-761.
22. Herget J, Holusa R, Paleček F. Pulmonary hypertension in rats with experimental emphysema. *Physiol Bohemoslov* 1974;23:55-65.
23. Herget J, Paleček F, Čermáková M, Vízek M. Pulmonary hypertension in rats with papain emphysema. *Respiration* 1979;38:204-212.
24. Herget J, Kuncová M, Havránková J, Paleček F. Pulmonary hypertension in silicotic rats. *Arch Environ Health* 1979;34:320-324.
25. Hampl V, Herget J. Role of nitric oxide in the pathogenesis of chronic pulmonary hypertension. *Physiol Rev* 2000;80:1337-1372.
26. Osada-Oka M, Ikeda T, Imaoka S, Akiba S, Sato T. VEGF-enhanced proliferation under hypoxia by an autocrine mechanism in human vascular smooth muscle cells. *J Atheroscler Thromb* 2008;15:26-33.
27. Böger R, Hannemann J. Dual role of the L-arginine-ADMA-NO pathway in systemic hypoxic vasodilation and pulmonary hypoxic vasoconstriction. *Pulm Circ* 2020;10:2045894020918850.
28. Hampl V, Bíbová J, Povýšilová V, Herget J. Dehydroepiandrosterone sulphate reduces chronic hypoxic pulmonary hypertension in rats. *Eur Respir J* 2003;21:862-865.
29. Herget J, Suggett AJ, Paleček F, Slavík Z. Effect of alpha-methyldopa on lung microembolism in the rat. *Bull Eur Physiopathol Respir* 1982;18:687-692.
30. Krása K, Vajnerová O, Ďurišová J, Minaříkova M, Miková D, Srbová M, Chalupský K, Kaftanová B, Hampl V. Simvastatin and dehydroepiandrosterone sulfate effects against hypoxic pulmonary hypertension are not additive. *Physiol Res* 2022;71:801-810.
31. Barnes H, Brown Z, Burns A, Williams T. Phosphodiesterase 5 inhibitors for pulmonary hypertension. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev* 2019;1:CD012621.
32. Ooi H, Cadogan E, Sweeney M, Howell K, O'Regan RG, McLoughlin P. Chronic hypercapnia inhibits hypoxic pulmonary vascular remodeling. *Am J Physiol Heart Circ Physiol* 2000;278:H331-H338.
33. Žaloudíková M, Herget J, Vízek M. Hypercapnia attenuates the hypoxia-induced blunting of the reactivity in chronically hypoxic rats. *Physiol Res* 2013;62:585-588.
34. Herget J, Pelouch V, Kolář F, Ošťádal B. The inhibition of angiotensin converting enzyme attenuates the effects of chronic hypoxia on pulmonary blood vessels in the rat. *Physiol Res* 1996;45:221-226.
35. Herget J, Bíbová J, Novotná J. [Mechanisms of remodeling of pulmonary blood vessels in chronic hypoxia]. *Cesk Fysiol* 1999;48:179-184.
36. Herget J, Wilhelm J, Novotná J, Eckhardt A, Vytásek R, Mrázková L, Ošťádal M. A possible role of the oxidant tissue injury in the development of hypoxic pulmonary hypertension. *Physiol Res* 2000;49:493-501.

37. Hodyc D, Johnson E, Skoumalová A, Tkaczyk J, Maxová H, Vízek M, Herget J. Reactive oxygen species production in the early and later stage of chronic ventilatory hypoxia. *Physiol Res* 2012;61:145-151.
38. Vajner L, Vytášek R, Lachmanová V, Uhlík J, Konrádová V, Novotná J, Hampl V, Herget J. Acute and chronic hypoxia as well as 7-day recovery from chronic hypoxia affects the distribution of pulmonary mast cells and their MMP-13 expression in rats. *Int J Exp Pathol* 2006;87:383-391.
39. Maxová H, Novotná J, Vajner L, Tomášová H, Vytášek R, Vízek M, Bačáková L, Valoušková V, Eliášová T, Herget J. In vitro hypoxia increases production of matrix metalloproteinases and trypsin in isolated rat lung mast cells. *Physiol Res* 2008;57:903-910.
40. Maxová H, Bačáková L, Lisá V, Novotná J, Tomášová H, Vízek M, Herget J. Production of proteolytic enzymes in mast cells, fibroblasts, vascular smooth muscle and endothelial cells cultivated under normoxic or hypoxic conditions. *Physiol Res* 2010;59:711-719.
41. Gallardo-Vara E, Ntokou A, Dave JM, Jovin DG, Saddouk FZ, Greif DM. Vascular pathobiology of pulmonary hypertension. *J Heart Lung Transplant* 2023;42:544-552.
42. Stenmark KR, Bouche D, Nemenoff R, Dempsey EC, Das M. Hypoxia-induced pulmonary vascular remodeling: contribution of the adventitial fibroblasts. *Physiol Res* 2000;49:503-517.
43. Nozik-Grayck E, Stenmark KR. Role of reactive oxygen species in chronic hypoxia-induced pulmonary hypertension and vascular remodeling. *Adv Exp Med Biol* 2007;618:101-112.
44. Burdon RH. Control of cell proliferation by reactive oxygen species. *Biochem Soc Trans* 1996;24:1028-1032.
45. Bačáková L, Herget J, Wilhelm J. Influence of macrophages and macrophage-modified collagen I on the adhesion and proliferation of vascular smooth muscle cells in culture. *Physiol Res* 1999;48:341-351.
46. Plecítá-Hlavatá L, D'Alessandro A, El Kasmi K, Li M, Zhang H, Ježek P, Stenmark KR. Metabolic Reprogramming and Redox Signaling in Pulmonary Hypertension. *Adv Exp Med Biol* 2017;967:241-260.
47. Bačáková L, Wilhelm J, Herget J, Novotná J, Eckhart A. Oxidized collagen stimulates proliferation of vascular smooth muscle cells. *Exp Mol Pathol* 1997;64:185-194.
48. Bačáková L, Lisá V, Kubínová L, Wilhelm J, Novotná J, Eckhart A, Herget J. Ultraviolet light-irradiated collagen III modulates expression of cytoskeletal and surface adhesion molecules in rat aortic smooth muscle cells in vitro. *Virchows Arch* 2002;440:50-62.
49. Stenmark KR, Frid MG, Graham BB, Tudor RM. Dynamic and diverse changes in the functional properties of vascular smooth muscle cells in pulmonary hypertension. *Cardiovasc Res* 2018;114:551-564.
50. Wilhelm J, Sojková J, Herget J. Production of hydrogen peroxide by alveolar macrophages from rats exposed to subacute and chronic hypoxia. *Physiol Res* 1996;45:185-191.
51. Bacakova L, Travnickova M, Filova E, Matějka R, Stepanovska J, Musilkova J, Zarubova J, Molitor M. The role of vascular smooth muscle cells in the physiology and pathophysiology of blood vessels. In: *Muscle cell and Tissue*. K SAKUMA (ed). IntechOpen, London, United Kingdom, 2018. pp 229-256.
52. Huang X, Akgün EE, Mehmood K, Zhang H, Tang Z, Li Y. Mechanism of Hypoxia-Mediated Smooth Muscle Cell Proliferation Leading to Vascular Remodeling. *Biomed Res Int* 2022;2022:3959845.
53. D'Alessandro A, El Kasmi KC, Plecítá-Hlavatá L, Ježek P, Li M, Zhang H, Gupte SA, Stenmark KR. Hallmarks of Pulmonary Hypertension: Mesenchymal and Inflammatory Cell Metabolic Reprogramming. *Antioxid Redox Signal* 2018;28:230-250.
54. Žaloudíková M. Mechanisms and Effects of Macrophage Polarization and Its Specifics in Pulmonary Environment. *Physiol Res* 2023;72:S137-S156.
55. Žaloudíková M, Vytášek R, Rašková M, Vízek M, Uhlík J, Hampl V. The effect of exposure to hypoxia on superoxide formation by alveolar macrophages is indirect. *Life Sci* 2019;236:116864.

56. Novotná J, Herget J. Exposure to chronic hypoxia induces qualitative changes of collagen in the walls of peripheral pulmonary arteries. *Life Sci* 1998;62:1-12.
57. Novotná J, Herget J. Possible role of matrix metalloproteinases in reconstruction of peripheral pulmonary arteries induced by hypoxia. *Physiol Res* 2002;51:323-334.
58. Bačáková L, Herget J, Novotná J, Eckhardt A, Lisá V. Adhesion, growth and stress adaptation of vascular smooth muscle cells in cultures on collagen I degraded by matrix metalloproteinase - 13. *Ateroskleróza: metabolizmus, klinika a liečba* 2002;6:155-161.
59. Maxová H, Bačáková L, Eckhardt A, Mikšík I, Lisá V, Novotná J, Herget J. Growth of vascular smooth muscle cells on collagen I exposed to RBL-2H3 mastocytoma cells. *Cell Physiol Biochem* 2010;25:615-622.
60. Maxová H, Herget J, Vízek M. Lung mast cells and hypoxic pulmonary hypertension. *Physiol Res* 2012;61:1-11.
61. Roberts IS, Brenchley PE. Mast cells: the forgotten cells of renal fibrosis. *J Clin Pathol* 2000;53:858-862.
62. Žaloudíková M, Eckhardt A, Vytášek R, Uhlík J, Novotný T, Bačáková L, Musílková J, Hampl V. Decreased collagen VI in the tunica media of pulmonary vessels during exposure to hypoxia: a novel step in pulmonary arterial remodeling. *Pulm Circ* 2019;9:2045894019860747.
63. Shamhart PE, Meszaros JG. Non-fibrillar collagens: key mediators of post-infarction cardiac remodeling? *J Mol Cell Cardiol* 2010;48:530-537.
64. Cescon M, Gattazzo F, Chen P, Bonaldo P. Collagen VI at a glance. *J Cell Sci* 2015;128:3525-3531.
65. Wang J, Pan W. The Biological Role of the Collagen Alpha-3 (VI) Chain and Its Cleaved C5 Domain Fragment Endotrophin in Cancer. *Oncotargets Ther* 2020;13:5779-5793.
66. Sun K, Park J, Kim M, Scherer PE. Endotrophin, a multifaceted player in metabolic dysregulation and cancer progression, is a predictive biomarker for the response to PPAR γ agonist treatment. *Diabetologia* 2017;60:24-29.
67. Bačáková L, Pellicciari C, Bottone MG, Lisá V, Mareš V. A sex-related difference in the hypertrophic versus hyperplastic response of vascular smooth muscle cells to repeated passaging in culture. *Histol Histopathol* 2001;16:675-684.
68. Hu Y, Zhao Y, Li P, Lu H, Li H, Ge J. Hypoxia and panvascular diseases: exploring the role of hypoxia-inducible factors in vascular smooth muscle cells under panvascular pathologies. *Sci Bull (Beijing)* 2023;68:1954-1974.
69. Novák T, Žaloudíková M, Smolková P, Kaftanová B, Edlmanová J, Krása K, Hampl V. Hypoxia-inducible factors activator, roxadustat, increases pulmonary vascular resistance in rats. *Physiol Res* 2023;72:S587-S592.
70. Luo Y, Teng X, Zhang L, Chen J, Liu Z, Chen X, Zhao S, Yang S, Feng J, Yan X. CD146-HIF-1 α hypoxic reprogramming drives vascular remodeling and pulmonary arterial hypertension. *Nat Commun* 2019;10:3551.
71. Pullamsetti SS, Mamazhakypov A, Weissmann N, Seeger W, Savai R. Hypoxia-inducible factor signaling in pulmonary hypertension. *J Clin Invest* 2020;130:5638-5651.
72. Zhang W, Tao Z, Xu F, Diao Q, Li J, Zhou L, Miao Y, Xie S, Wan J, Xu R. An Overview of miRNAs Involved in PASMC Phenotypic Switching in Pulmonary Hypertension. *Biomed Res Int* 2021;2021:5765029.
73. Kumar S, Frid MG, Zhang H, Li M, Riddle S, Brown RD, Yadav SC, Roy MK, Dzieciatkowska ME, D'Alessandro A, Hansen KC, Stenmark KR. Complement-containing small extracellular vesicles from adventitial fibroblasts induce proinflammatory and metabolic reprogramming in macrophages. *JCI Insight* 2021;6:e148382.
74. Plecítá-Hlavatá L, Brázdová A, Křivonosková M, Hu CJ, Phang T, Tauber J, Li M, Zhang H, Hoetzenecker K, Crnkovic S, Kwapiszewska G, Stenmark KR. Microenvironmental regulation of T-cells in pulmonary hypertension. *Front Immunol* 2023;14:1223122.

75. Barman SA, Li XY, Haigh S, Kondrikov D, Mahboubi K, Bordan Z, Stepp DW, Zhou JL, Wang YS, Weintraub DN, Traber EE, Snider L, Jonigk D, Sullivan ENE, Crislip RY, Butcher JT, Thompson J, Su YC, Chen F, Fulton DJR. Galectin-3 is expressed in vascular smooth muscle cells and promotes pulmonary hypertension through changes in proliferation, apoptosis, and fibrosis. *Am J Physiol Lung Cell Mol Physiol* 2019;316:L784-L797.
76. Tian L, Chen K, Cao J, Han Z, Wang Y, Gao L, Fan Y, Wang C. Galectin-3 induces the phenotype transformation of human vascular smooth muscle cells via the canonical Wnt signaling. *Mol Med Rep* 2017;15:3840-3846.
77. Li T, Zha L, Luo H, Li S, Zhao L, He J, Li X, Qi Q, Liu Y, Yu Z. Galectin-3 Mediates Endothelial-to-Mesenchymal Transition in Pulmonary Arterial Hypertension. *Aging Dis* 2019;10:731-745.
78. Choo YY, Sakai T, Komatsu S, Ikebe R, Jeffers A, Singh KP, Idell S, Tucker TA, Ikebe M. Calponin 1 contributes to myofibroblast differentiation of human pleural mesothelial cells. *Am J Physiol Lung Cell Mol Physiol* 2022;322:L348-L364.
79. Bekhite MM, Finkensieper A, Rebhan J, Huse S, Schultze-Mosgau S, Figulla HR, Sauer H, Wartenberg M. Hypoxia, leptin, and vascular endothelial growth factor stimulate vascular endothelial cell differentiation of human adipose tissue-derived stem cells. *Stem Cells Dev* 2014;23:333-351.
80. Podkalicka P, Stepniewski J, Mucha O, Kachamakova-Trojanowska N, Dulak J, Łoboda A. Hypoxia as a Driving Force of Pluripotent Stem Cell Reprogramming and Differentiation to Endothelial Cells. *Biomolecules* 2020;10:1614.
81. Shimomura S, Inoue H, Arai Y, Nakagawa S, Fujii Y, Kishida T, Shin-Ya M, Ichimaru S, Tsuchida S, Mazda O, Kubo T. Hypoxia promotes differentiation of pure cartilage from human induced pluripotent stem cells. *Mol Med Rep* 2022;26:229.
82. Yu X, Wan Q, Ye X, Cheng Y, Pathak J, Li Z. Cellular hypoxia promotes osteogenic differentiation of mesenchymal stem cells and bone defect healing via STAT3 signaling. *Cell Mol Biol Lett* 2019;24:64.
83. Chen W, Zhuo Y, Duan D, Lu M. Effects of Hypoxia on Differentiation of Mesenchymal Stem Cells. *Curr Stem Cell Res Ther* 2020;15:332-339.
84. Lin J, Zhu Q, Huang J, Cai R, Kuang Y. Hypoxia Promotes Vascular Smooth Muscle Cell (VSMC) Differentiation of Adipose-Derived Stem Cell (ADSC) by Regulating Mettl3 and Paracrine Factors. *Stem Cells Int* 2020;2020:2830565.
85. Gui Y, Yin H, He JY, Yang SH, Walsh MP, Zheng XL. Endoreduplication of human smooth muscle cells induced by 2-methoxyestradiol: a role for cyclin-dependent kinase 2. *Am J Physiol Heart Circ Physiol* 2007;292:H1313-H1320.
86. Majka SM, Skokan M, Wheeler L, Harral J, Gladson S, Burnham E, Loyd JE, Stenmark KR, Varella-Garcia M, West J. Evidence for cell fusion is absent in vascular lesions associated with pulmonary arterial hypertension. *Am J Physiol Lung Cell Mol Physiol* 2008;295:L1028-L1039.
87. Orton EC, LaRue SM, Ensley B, Stenmark K. Bromodeoxyuridine labeling and DNA content of pulmonary arterial medial cells from hypoxia-exposed and nonexposed healthy calves. *Am J Vet Res* 1992;53:1925-1930.
88. Born E, Lipskaia L, Breaux M, Houssaini A, Beaulieu D, Marcos E, Pierre R, Do Cruzeiro M, Lefevre M, Derumeaux G, Bulavin DV, Delcroix M, Quarck R, Reen V, Gil J, Bernard D, Flaman JM, Adnot S, Abid S. Eliminating Senescent Cells Can Promote Pulmonary Hypertension Development and Progression. *Circulation* 2023;147:650-666.
89. Otani N, Tomoe T, Kawabe A, Sugiyama T, Horie Y, Sugimura H, Yasu T, Nakamoto T. Recent Advances in the Treatment of Pulmonary Arterial Hypertension. *Pharmaceuticals (Basel)* 2022;15:1277.
90. Sydykov A, Mamazhakypov A, Maripov A, Kosanovic D, Weissmann N, Ghofrani HA, Sarybaev AS, Schermuly RT. Pulmonary Hypertension in Acute and Chronic High Altitude Maladaptation Disorders. *Int J Environ Res Public Health* 2021;18:1692.

91. Redaelli S, Magliocca A, Malhotra R, Ristagno G, Citerio G, Bellani G, Berra L, Rezoagli E. Nitric oxide: Clinical applications in critically ill patients. *Nitric Oxide* 2022;121:20-33.
92. Rawat M, Lakshminrusimha S, Vento M. Pulmonary hypertension and oxidative stress: Where is the link? *Semin Fetal Neonatal Med* 2022;27:101347.
93. Duong-Quy S, Bei Y, Liu Z, Dinh-Xuan AT. Role of Rho-kinase and its inhibitors in pulmonary hypertension. *Pharmacol Ther* 2013;137:352-364.
94. Nathan SD, Barbera JA, Gaine SP, Harari S, Martinez FJ, Olschewski H, Olsson KM, Peacock AJ, Pepke-Zaba J, Provencher S, Weissmann N, Seeger W. Pulmonary hypertension in chronic lung disease and hypoxia. *Eur Respir J* 2019;53:1801914.
95. Zolty R. Novel Experimental Therapies for Treatment of Pulmonary Arterial Hypertension. *J Exp Pharmacol* 2021;13:817-857.
96. Wan JJ, Yi J, Wang FY, Zhang C, Dai AG. Expression and regulation of HIF-1a in hypoxic pulmonary hypertension: Focus on pathological mechanism and pharmacological treatment. *Int J Med Sci* 2024;21:45-60.
97. El Alam S, Pena E, Aguilera D, Siques P, Brito J. Inflammation in Pulmonary Hypertension and Edema Induced by Hypobaric Hypoxia Exposure. *Int J Mol Sci* 2022;23:12656.
98. Flores K, Siques P, Brito J, Arribas SM. AMPK and the Challenge of Treating Hypoxic Pulmonary Hypertension. *Int J Mol Sci* 2022;23:6205.
99. Sedlář A, Trávníčková M, Bojarová P, Vlachová M, Slámová K, Křen V, Bačáková L. Interaction between Galectin-3 and Integrins Mediates Cell-Matrix Adhesion in Endothelial Cells and Mesenchymal Stem Cells. *Int J Mol Sci* 2021;22:5144.
100. Sedlář A, Vrbata D, Pokorná K, Holzerová K, Červený J, Kočková O, Hlaváčková M, Doubková M, Musílková J, Křen V, Kolář F, Bačáková L, Bojarová P. Glycopolymer inhibitors of galectin-3 suppress the markers of tissue remodeling in pulmonary hypertension. *J Med Chem*, accepted.